

The Influence of Brand Trust, Brand Image and Perceived Quality on Pepsodent Toothpaste Brand Loyalty (Study on the Community of Tuah Madani District, Pekanbaru City)

Ferizal Rachmad

Universitas Islam Negeri Sultan Syarif Kasim Riau, Pekanbaru

*Email : ferizal@uin-suska.ac.id

Mardatilla

Universitas Islam Negeri Sultan Syarif Kasim Riau, Pekanbaru

Email : mardatilla@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to determine whether the influence of Brand Trust, Brand Image and Perception of Quality on Brand Loyalty in the community of tuah madani sub-district, pekanbaru city. The rapid development of the company has led to intense competition between companies to win the hearts of consumers. This is indicated by the increasing number of companies that produce similar products, in order to meet consumer needs. The data collection technique used a questionnaire. The population in this study were pepsodent toothpaste users in the tuah madani sub-district of pekanbaru city 2024. In this study, the sample amounted to 100 respondents using purposive sampling technique. Data analysis used in this study is quantitative with multiple linear regression methods. Based on the results of the simultaneous test, it can be seen that the variables of brand trust, brand image and perceived quality together have an effect on the loyalty of the pepsodent toothpaste brand in the community of tuah madani subdistrict, pekanbaru city. Then test partially, from this test it can be seen that the brand trust variable has a significant effect on brand loyalty and the brand image variable has a significant effect on brand loyalty and perceived quality has a significant effect on brand loyalty. Obtained R square value of 0.737 or equal to 73.7% while the remaining 26.3% is influenced by other variables not included in this study.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of companies has led to intense competition between companies to win the hearts of consumers. This is indicated by the increasing number of companies that produce similar products, in order to meet consumer needs. With so many choices of products in the market, consumers will find it difficult to analyze the products they want to buy. One of the things that companies can do to anticipate this is to develop a strong identity through brands. Brand loyalty is a competitive advantage that can describe how loyalty to a particular product. Loyalty measures can provide an overview of how consumers choose an item for a long period and do not turn to other products. Loyal consumers will make repeat purchases and have the enthusiasm to inform anyone the products they use to consumers they know. There are many factors that can affect the decline in brand loyalty, such as brand trust, brand image, consumer perceptions of quality, toothpaste products with the Pepsodent brand for three consecutive years occupied the first rank position of

the Top Brand Award from 2018 to 2020 even though the percentage fluctuates every year and the market share of toothpaste brand pepsodent which is often used by 76% of respondents in the past year. This happens because of the increasing number of competitors in toothpaste products such as ciptadent, close up, formula, sensodyne, which results in ups and downs in the percentage level but the Pepsodent brand is still ranked first on the Top Brand list of toothpaste product brands.

LITRATURE REVIEW

A. Theory Brand Loyalty

Brand loyalty is defined as a form of intrinsic consumer commitment to carry out repeated purchasing activities for a brand (Abdullah, 2015). Based on the opinion of (Schiffman, L. G. Wisenblit, 2015) brand loyalty is a process carried out by consumers in studying purchases on certain brands without paying attention to other alternatives to the same type of product. According to (Rangkuti, 2016) brand loyalty is a measure of consumer loyalty to a brand.

B. Theory Brand Trust

Definition of Brand Trust According to (Diana, 2016) that the trust factor in a brand is a crucial aspect in the formation of brand purchase intention. They define trust in a brand as the willingness of consumers to trust or rely on brands in risk situations due to the expectation that the brand in question will provide positive results. According to (Beneker, J., Adams, 2017) brand trust is the brand's ability to be trusted (brand reliability), which is based on consumer confidence that the product is able to fulfill the promised value and good brand intention (brand intention) which is based on consumer confidence that the brand is able to prioritize consumer interests.

C. Theory Brand Image

According to (Effendi et al., 2022) brand image is a description of consumer associations and beliefs about certain brands.

Brand image can be thought of as a type of association that comes to mind when consumers recall a particular brand. Such associations can simply appear in the form of certain thoughts or images associated with a brand, just as when someone thinks about another person. These associations can be conceptualized based on type, support, strength, and uniqueness. Types of brand associations include attributes, benefits, and attitudes. Attributes consist of product-related attributes, such as price, user, and usage image. While benefits include functional benefits, symbolic benefits, and experiential benefits (A. Shimp, 2014) A product that can maintain its image to be better than competitors will get a place in the hearts of consumers and will always be remembered.

D. Theory Perceived Quality

According to (Duriyanto, 2014) Perception of quality is the customer's perception of the overall quality or superiority of a product or service in relation to what the customer expects. Perceived quality can be defined as the customer's perception of the overall quality or superiority of a product or service compared to what the customer expects.

E. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Collection of Research (2020)

METHOD

Menurut metodenya, This research is a type of research in the academic field, using survey (research methods) and using the (level of explanation). The population to be studied in this study are the people of tuah madani sub-district in Pekanbaru who use pepsodent toothpaste products. The population size of this study is not clearly known. Sampling technique purposive sampling using questionnaires. which amounted to 100 samples. The variables used in this study are: brand trust (X1), brand image (X2), perceived quality (X3), and brand loyalty (Y).

For testing in this study, :

1. Data Quality Test (Instrumen)

a. Test of Validity

The validity test is an index that shows the measuring instrument actually measures what is being measured. This validity concerns the accuracy of the experiment. Validity testing was carried out to test whether the questionnaire answers from respondents were really suitable for use in this study or not (Sanaky, 2021).

b. Test of Reliability

Reliability is an index that shows the extent to which a measuring instrument can be trusted or reliable. Reliability is also a term used to indicate the extent to which the measurement results are relatively consistent if the measurement is repeated two or more times. If a measuring instrument is used twice to measure the same symptoms and the measurement results obtained are relatively consistent, the measuring instrument is reliable. In other words, reliability shows the consistency of a measuring instrument in measuring the same symptoms (Ardianto, 2017).

2. Classical Assumption Test

a. Data Normality Test

The normality test is a test to determine whether the regression model is normally distributed or not. A good regression model must have normally distributed data. The test used in this study is a statistical test with Kolmogorof-Smirnov (Suliyanto, 2019).

b. Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to test whether the regression model obtained has a correlation between the independent variables (Ghozali, 2016).

c. Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity testing in the regression model is carried out to determine whether in the regression model there is an inequality of variance from residual observations to other observations (Suliyanto, 2019).

3. Hypothesis Test

In this study, hypothesis testing using multiple regression, multiple linear regression analysis is an analytical tool used to measure the effect of two or more independent variables on the dependent variable. (Suliyanto, 2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Data Quality Test (Instrumen)

a. Test of Validity

Table 1. Test of Validity Brand Loyalty

No	Questions	Corrected item total	R-table	sig	Description
		correlation			
1.	P1	0.656	0.196	0.000	Valid
2.	P2	0.799	0.196	0.000	Valid
3.	P3	0.777	0.196	0.000	Valid
4.	P4	0.786	0.196	0.000	Valid
5.	P5	0.771	0.196	0.000	Valid
6.	P6	0.745	0.196	0.000	Valid

Source : Processed Data, 2024

Table 2. Test of Validity Brand Trust

No	Questions	Corrected item total	R-table	Sig	Description
		correlation			
1.	P1	0.864	0.196	0.000	Valid
2.	P2	0.906	0.196	0.000	Valid
3.	P3	0.840	0.196	0.000	valid

Source : Processed Data, 2024

Table 3. Test of Validity Brand Image

No	Questions	Corrected item total	R-table	sig	Description
		correlation			
1.	P1	0.823	0.196	0.000	Valid
2.	P2	0.869	0.196	0.000	Valid
3.	P3	0.874	0.196	0.000	Valid

Source : Processed Data, 2024

Table 4. Test of Validity Quality Perception

No	Questions	Corrected item total	R-table	sig	Description
		correlation			
1.	P1	0.906	0.196	0.000	Valid
2.	P2	0.921	0.196	0.000	Valid
3.	P3	0.863	0.196	0.000	Valid

Source : Processed Data, 2024

b. Test of Reliability

Table 5. Test of Reliability

No	Variable	Nilai Cronbach's Alpha	Batas Cronbach's Alpha	Description
1	Brand Loyalty	0.848	0.60	Reliable
2	Brand Trust	0.837	0.60	Reliable
3	Brand Image	0.815	0.60	Reliable
4	Quality Perception	0.874	0.60	Reliable

Source : Processed Data, 2024

2. Classical Assumption Test

a. Data Normality Test

Table 6. Data Normality Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.79756333
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.083
	Positive	.041
	Negative	-.083
Test Statistic		.083
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.083 ^c

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

Source : Processed Data, 2024

b. Multicollinearity Test

Table 7. Multicollinearity Test**Coefficients^a**

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	KEPERCAYAAN MEREK	.460	2.174
	CITRA MEREK	.325	3.076
	PERSEPSI KUALITAS	.317	3.159

a. Dependent Variable: LOYALITAS MEREK

Source : Processed Data, 2024

c. Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 8. Heteroscedasticity Test

Source : Processed Data, 2024

3. Hypothesis Test

Table 9. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.201	1.092		6.595	.000
	KEPERCAYAAN MEREK	.410	.107	.295	3.825	.000
	CITRA MEREK	.489	.147	.305	3.322	.001
	PERSEPSI KUALITAS	.546	.146	.347	3.730	.000

a. Dependent Variable: LOYALITAS MEREK

Source : Processed Data, 2024

The explanation presented regarding the influence of Brand Trust, Brand Image, and Perceived Quality on Brand Loyalty, especially on Pepsodent toothpaste products in the Tuah Madani District Community, Pekanbaru City, provides interesting insight into how consumers develop brand loyalty. The following is a detailed explanation of the findings:

Partial Influence

1. Brand Trust: Identified as the variable with the greatest influence on Brand Loyalty. This suggests that consumer trust in the Pepsodent brand is critical in building loyalty. Consumers who trust the quality, effectiveness, and consistency of the product tend to remain loyal.
2. Brand Image: Its influence on brand loyalty suggests that consumers' perceptions of Pepsodent's image, including positive associations and brand reputation, contribute to their loyalty. A strong brand image can attract consumers and encourage repeat purchases.

3. Perceived Quality: The influence of perceived quality on brand loyalty underscores the importance of products meeting or exceeding consumer expectations. Consumers who are satisfied with product quality tend to remain loyal.

Simultaneous Influence

All three variables, when considered together, have a significant influence on Brand Loyalty. This suggests that the combination of brand trust, brand image, and overall perceived quality strongly influences Pepsodent brand loyalty in the community.

Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The R^2 value of 0.737 or 73.7% indicates that about 73.7% of the variation in brand loyalty can be explained by the Brand Trust, Brand Image, and Perceived Quality variables. This is a fairly high level of explanation, indicating that these three variables are important determinants of brand loyalty in this context. The remaining 26.3% of variation in brand loyalty may be influenced by other factors not examined in this study, such as marketing influence, social factors, personal experience with the product, or overall consumer satisfaction.

Overall, the findings provide valuable insights for Pepsodent management in designing more effective marketing and product strategies to enhance trust, strengthen image, and guarantee perceived quality, in order to increase brand loyalty among its consumers.

CONCLUSION

Partially Brand Trust, Brand Image and Perceived Quality have an influence on Pepsodent toothpaste Brand Loyalty in the Tuah Madani District Community, Pekanbaru City with the variable that has a greater influence, namely Brand Trust.

Simultaneously Brand Trust, Brand Image and Perception of Quality have an influence on Brand Loyalty of Pepsodent toothpaste in the Community of Tuah Madani District, Pekanbaru City.

Based on the calculation of the Coefficient of Determination (R^2), the R square value is 0.737 or 73.7%. This shows that the variables of Brand Trust, Brand Image and Perception of Quality as a whole have an influence of 73.7% on the Brand Loyalty variable. While the remaining 26.3% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

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